

A APPENDIX: DASHBOARDS ANALYSIS BASED ON ISO FEATURE MODEL

This appendix will be provided as an online PDF document in the final version of the paper. It is now included in the PDF for the convenience of the reviewers.

Dashboard	Features	Comments
D01: C2SMART Mobility Dashboard [65]	TRVINP-TRFI_TrafficFlows TRVINP-ASERV_Buses TRVINP-ASERV_Subways TRVINP-ASERV_ConmuterRails TRVINP-ASERV_Bikes TRVINP-ASERV_Taxi TRAFM-TRMON_Speed TRAFM-TRMON_FlowRate TRAFM-TRMON_Congestion	Contemplated in ISO - D.2.2.1 weight in motion - J.2.2.1 Disaster and emergency data collection NOT Contemplated in ISO - Daily Freight Trip in New York City (F.01) - Speeding Tickets (F.02)
D02: WSDOT Washington State [82]	TRVINP-TRFI_TrafficFlows TRVINP-ASERV_Ferrys TRVINP-ASERV_Airports TRVINP-ASERV_Wheelchairs TRVINP-ASERV_Pedestrians TRVINP-ASERV_SpecialVehicle TRVINP-ASERV_Buses TRVINP-ASERV_Subways	Contemplated in ISO - D.2.2.1 Weight in motion - J.2.2.1 Disaster and emergency data collection
D03: PTV Accesibility [62]		NOT Contemplated in ISO - Accesibility (F.03)
D04: IDASO Galway City Council [69]	TRVINP-ASERV_Cars TRVINP-ASERV_Buses TRVINP-ASERV_Scooters TRVINP-ASERV_SpecialVehicles TRVINP-TRSERV-D_Hotels TRVINP-TRSERV-D_Restaurants TRVINP-TRSERV-D_OtherServices TRVINP-TRSERV-EntPlaces TRAFM-TRMON_FlowRate TRAFM-TRMON_Speed	NOT Contemplated in ISO - Mobility trends for: (F.04) - Shopping - Parks - Residence - Retail - Transit workplace
D05: Transportation dashboards Austin gov [66]	TRVINP-TRFI_TrafficFlows TRVINP-ASERV_Bikes TRVINP-ASERV_Scooters TRVINP-ASERV_SpecialVehicles	Contemplated in ISO - J.2.2.1 Disaster and emergency data collection NOT Contemplated in ISO - Visualizations for vehicle type / demography, demografia (F.05) - Signal monitoring (F.06)
D06: Mohua Government [75]	TRVINP-ASERV_Bikes TRVINP-ASERV_Pedestrians	NOT Contemplated in ISO - Sidewalks (F.07) - Cycle lane overage (F.08) - Visualizations for vehicle type/ demography (F.05) - Bus availability
D07: Mobility analyst [74]	TRVINP-ASERV_Pedestrians TRVINP-ASERV_Bikes TRVINP-ASERV_Scooters TRVINP-ASERV_SpecialVehicles W-ENV-POLLM_VehicleExhausts W-ENV-POLLM_Stations TRVINP-INTFAC-S_TransferPointsLoc TRVINP-INTFAC-S_TransferModes TRVINP-INTFAC-S_TransferFacilities TRVINP-INTFAC-D_ServiceAvailability PT-M-RTI-VS_Status	Contemplated in ISO - A.2.2.5 Parking information NOT Contemplated in ISO - Charging points (F.09)

Dashboard	Features	Comments
D08: Belgian Mobility Dashboard [63]	TRAFM-TRMON_Congestion TRVINF-ASERV_Trains TRVINF-ASERV_Buses TRVINF-ASERV_Trams TRVINF-ASERV_Bikes TRVINF-INTFAC-_TransferPointsLoc TRVINF-INTFAC-S_TransferFacilities W-ENV-POLLM_VehicleExhausts PT-FLM_PerformanceMonitor	Contemplated in ISO - J.2.2.1 Disaster and emergency data collection - E.2.2.4 Bicycle racks - A.2.2.2 Public transport information - Public transport punctuality - Most delayed routes - Delay of each station NOT Contemplated in ISO - Charging stations (F.09) - Car registrations (motorbike, light trucks, heavy trucks) (F.10)
D09: French economic dashboard [71]	TRVINF-ASERV_Buses TRVINF-ASERV_Trams TRVINF-ASERV_Cars TRVINF-ASERV_Pedestrians TRVINF-ASERV_Bikes TRVINF-INTFAC-_TransferModes	
D10: Kingston in focus [72]	TRVINF-TRFI_SpetialConds TRVINF-TRFI_RoadwayState TRVINF-ASERV_Buses TRVINF-ASERV_Trams TRAFM-DVCOND_RoadWorks TRVINF-TRSERV-D_Medical	NOT Contemplated in ISO - Sidewalks (F.07) - Cycle lane coverage (F.08) - Parks TRVINF-TRSERV-D_Parks (F.11) - Groceries TRVINF-TRSERV-D_Groceries (F.12) - Travel to parks (F.04)
D11: US Micromobility equity Requirements [64]	TRVINF-ASERV_Bikes TRVINF-ASERV_Scooters TRVINF-INTFAC-S_TransferPointsLoc TRVINF-INTFAC-_TransferFacilities	
D12: MoDD [76]	TRVINF-ASERV_Cars TRVINF-ASERV_Pedestrians TRVINF-ASERV_Buses TRVINF-ASERV_Subways TRVINF-ASERV_Tram TRVINF-ASERV_Bikes TRVINF-INTFAC-_TransferPointsLoc TRVINF-INTFAC-S_TransferModes TRVINF-INTFAC-S_TransferFacilities	NOT Contemplated in ISO - Sidewalks/Walkability (F.07) - Cycle lane coverage (F.08)
D13: City of San Jose [67]	TRVINF-ASERV_Pedestrians TRVINF-ASERV_Bikes TRVINF-ASERV_Cars TRVINF-INTFAC-S_TransferPointsLoc	Contemplated in ISO - D.2.2.1 Weight in motion NOT Contemplated in ISO - Car registrations (motorbike, light trucks, heavy trucks) (F.10)
D14: Texas A&M transportation Institute [81]	TRAFM-TRMON_Congestion TRAFM-TRMON_Headway TRAFM-TRMON_FlowRate TRAFM-DVCOND_TrafficCongestion	
D15: MassDOT Mobility dashboard [73]	TRAFM-TRMON_FlowRate TRAFM-TRMON_Congestion TRAFM-TRMON_Speed TRVINF-ASERV_Buses	
D18: Traffic flow [79]	TRVINF-TRFI_TrafficFlows	

Dashboard	Features	Comments
D19: Snap4city mobility and what-if analysis [80]	TRVINP-TRFI_TrafficFlows TRAFM-TRMON_FlowRate TRAFM-TRMON_Speed TRAFM-TRMON_Congestion TRAFM-DVCOND_TrafficCongestion TRAFM-ADVCOND_Weather W-ENV-POLLM_Stations TRVINP-ASERV_Buses TRVINP-ASERV_Trans TRVINP-ASERV_Cars TRVINP-SERV_ConmuterRails TRVINP-ASERV_Bikes	Contemplated in ISO - J.2.2.1 Disaster and emergency data collection NOT Contemplated in ISO - Cycle lane coverage (F.08)
D20: Micromobility Dashboard Australia [78]	TRVINP-ASERV_Buses TRVINP-ASERV_Trans TRVINP-ASERV_Cars TRVINP-ASERV_ConmuterRails TRVINP-SERV_Bikes	
D21: HKSmart City Blueprint [70]	TRVINP-TRFI_TrafficFlows TRAFM-TRMON_FlowRate TRAFM-RMON_Congestion TRAFM-ADVCOND_TrafficCongestion	
D22: SFMTA [61]	TRVINP-ASERV_Bikes	Contemplated in ISO - E.2.2.4 Bicycle racks * NOT Contemplated in ISO - Shared mobility citations (F.13) - Shared mobility complaints - Shared mobility fines and fees
D23: Safe mobility [68]		Contemplated in ISO - J.2.2.1 Disaster and emergency data collection
D24: Austin texas gov [77]	TRVINP-NTFAC-S_TransferModes TRVINP-INTFAC-D_ServiceAvailability TRVINP-TRFI_TrafficFlows TRVINP-TRFI_SpetialConds TRAFM-TRMON_Congestion	Contemplated in ISO - J.2.2.1 Disaster and emergency data collection NOT Contemplated in ISO - Sidewalks/Walkability (F.07) - Cycle ane coverage (F.08) - Transportation cost (F.14) - Percent split of modes based on commute to work (mode share) (F.15)

URLS OF THE DASHBOARDS

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